

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX
METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART IV.
THERMOMETRIC STUDY OF THE COMPOSITION
OF CADMIUM FERROCYANIDE

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The composition of cadmium ferrocyanide has been studied by the thermometric method by the direct and the reverse methods in aqueous and in aqueous alcoholic media. The composition arrived at approximates to $K_2CdFeCy_6$, and is also affected by factors such as hydrolysis and adsorption.

Wyrouboff (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1876, v, 8, 444) found that whatever be the proportion of cadmium salt relative to potassium ferrocyanide, the composition of the precipitate corresponded to $K_6Cd_6[(FeCy_6)]_4$. When precipitated in ammoniacal solution, the precipitate was found by Miller and Fisher (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 22, 537) to correspond to $K_2CdFeCy_6$, while in acid solution its composition was found by them to lie between this and the one proposed by Wyrouboff. This was confirmed by Mackay (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 940) who stated that it required about 2.5% less potassium ferrocyanide to precipitate cadmium than would be required by $K_2CdFeCy_6$. Miller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 226) on the other hand found that $K_2CdFeCy_6$ was precipitated with K_4FeCy_6 in excess only from an alkaline or acid medium, whilst the one from neutral salt contained a larger proportion of Cd. With cadmium in excess, the composition of the precipitate in neutral solution was found to correspond with $K_8Cd_{10}(FeCy_6)_7$.

Treadwell and Chervat (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 15, 633) found by electrometric titrations, that only in highly dilute solutions the precipitate approximated to the composition $K_2CdFeCy_6$. Koltzoff (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1923, 62, 209) followed the method of conductometric titrations and concluded that at first the normal salt $K_2CdFeCy_6$ was precipitated, which, with further quantity of the reagent, gave the double salt $K_2Cd_2(FeCy_6)_2$.

In view of these conflicting opinions it was considered worthwhile to study the composition of this compound by thermometric, conductometric and potentiometric methods of analysis, with a view to arriving at a more definite conclusion. In this paper the results of thermometric titrations have been discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The arrangement for the thermometric titrations was similar to the one used by Haldar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 147). Reagents used were of 'Analar' (B. D. H.) quality. Cadmium sulphate solution was estimated by the electrolytic method. Potassium ferrocyanide solution was estimated by titrating against standardised potassium permanganate solution (Treadwell and Hall "Analytical Chemistry", Part II, p. 536).

Using different concentrations of the two salt solutions the titrations were followed by the direct and the reverse methods. The titrations were also made in the presence of alcohol up to a total concentration of 20% by volume.

M/5.41 solution of cadmium sulphate would be referred as A/1 solution of CdSO_4 and M/4.99 solution of potassium ferrocyanide as A/1 solution of K_4FeCy_6 .

Direct Thermometric Titrations

Cadmium sulphate from the burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide solution taken in the thermo-flask and mixed with varying amounts of alcohol.

TABLE I

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 = 20 c.c.
Alcohol = nil.
(Fig. 1, curve 1).

A/2- CdSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
0.5	0.030
1.0	0.065
1.5	0.095
2.0	0.120
2.5	0.155
3.0	0.185
3.5	0.215
4.0	0.250
4.5	0.280
5.0	0.305
5.5	0.315
6.0	0.330
6.5	0.340
7.0	0.350
7.5	0.360
8.0	0.365

TABLE II

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2 c.c.
(Fig. 1, curve 2).

A/2- CdSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
0.5	0.040
1.0	0.080
1.5	0.125
2.0	0.170
2.5	0.215
3.0	0.255
3.5	0.290
4.0	0.330
4.5	0.355
5.0	0.375
5.5	0.390
6.0	0.400
6.5	0.410
7.0	0.425
7.5	0.440

TABLE III

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c.c.
(Fig. 1, curve 3).

A/2- CdSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
0.5	0.050
1.0	0.110
1.5	0.185
2.0	0.255
2.5	0.315
3.0	0.390
3.5	0.450
4.0	0.495
4.5	0.520
5.0	0.540
5.5	0.570
6.0	0.595
6.5	0.620

TABLE IV

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 = 20 c.c.
Alcohol = nil.
(Fig. 2, curve 4).

A/4- CdSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
1.0	0.060
2.0	0.125
3.0	0.180
4.0	0.240
5.0	0.290
6.0	0.345
7.0	0.390
8.0	0.440
9.0	0.480
10.0	0.510
11.0	0.540
12.0	0.560
13.0	0.575
14.0	0.590
15.0	0.610

TABLE V

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2 c.c.
(Fig. 2, curve 5).

A/4- CdSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
1.0	0.055
2.0	0.110
3.0	0.165
4.0	0.210
5.0	0.265
6.0	0.320
7.0	0.360
8.0	0.395
9.0	0.420
10.0	0.445
11.0	0.465
12.0	0.485
13.0	0.500

TABLE VI

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c.c.
(Fig. 2, curve 6).

A/4- CdSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
1.0	0.080
2.0	0.210
3.0	0.330
4.0	0.430
5.0	0.520
6.0	0.600
7.0	0.660
8.0	0.720
9.0	0.760
10.0	0.800
11.0	0.830
12.0	0.860
13.0	0.880

Reverse Thermometric Titrations

Potassium ferrocyanide from burette was added to cadmium sulphate in the thermo-flask, and mixed with varying amounts of alcohol.

TABLE VII

A/10-CdSO₄ = 20 c.c.
Alcohol = nil.
(Fig. 3, curve 7).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
0.5	0.005
1.0	0.020
1.5	0.040
2.0	0.060
2.5	0.075
3.0	0.100
3.5	0.120
4.0	0.145
4.5	0.165
5.0	0.185
5.5	0.205
6.0	0.230
6.5	0.255
7.0	0.265
7.5	0.275
8.0	0.280
8.5	0.295
9.0	0.305

TABLE VIII

A/10-CdSO₄ = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2 c.c.
(Fig. 3, curve 8).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
0.5	0.030
1.0	0.050
1.5	0.080
2.0	0.110
2.5	0.140
3.0	0.175
3.5	0.200
4.0	0.230
4.5	0.255
5.0	0.285
5.5	0.315
6.0	0.335
6.5	0.350
7.0	0.360
7.5	0.370
8.0	0.385
8.5	0.400

TABLE IX

A/10-CdSO₄ = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c.c.
(Fig. 3, curve 9).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
0.5	0.040
1.0	0.085
1.5	0.140
2.0	0.185
2.5	0.240
3.0	0.285
3.5	0.330
4.0	0.365
4.5	0.415
5.0	0.445
5.5	0.485
6.0	0.505
6.5	0.525
7.0	0.545
7.5	0.555
8.0	0.570
8.5	0.585

TABLE X

A/10-CdSO₄ = 20 c.c.
Alcohol = nil.
(Fig. 4, curve 10).

A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
2.0	0.000
3.0	0.005
4.0	0.015
5.0	0.030
6.0	0.045
7.0	0.065
8.0	0.085
9.0	0.105
10.0	0.125
11.0	0.145
12.0	0.165
13.0	0.185
14.0	0.205
15.0	0.215
16.0	0.225
17.0	0.235
18.0	0.245
19.0	0.255

TABLE XI

A/10-CdSO₄ = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2 c.c.
(Fig. 4, curve 11).

A/6-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
1.0	0.025
2.0	0.050
3.0	0.090
4.0	0.130
5.0	0.165
6.0	0.200
7.0	0.235
8.0	0.270
9.0	0.300
10.0	0.330
11.0	0.350
12.0	0.380
13.0	0.400
14.0	0.410
15.0	0.420
16.0	0.430
17.0	0.440
18.0	0.440
19.0	0.450

TABLE XII

A/10-CdSO₄ = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c.c.
(Fig. 4, curve 12).

A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000°
2.0	0.090
3.0	0.180
4.0	0.265
5.0	0.340
6.0	0.405
7.0	0.465
8.0	0.520
9.0	0.575
10.0	0.620
11.0	0.660
12.0	0.695
13.0	0.725
14.0	0.750
15.0	0.775
16.0	0.785
17.0	0.800
18.0	0.810
19.0	0.825

DISCUSSION

Considering the strengths of the solutions of cadmium sulphate ($M/5.41$) and potassium ferrocyanide ($M/4.99$), theoretical titre values required for 20 c.c. of K_4FeCy_6 for the formation of the compounds $K_2CdFeCy_6$, Cd_2FeCy_6 and $K_2Cd_3(FeCy_6)_2$ in direct titrations would be 21.68, 43.36, and 32.52 c.c. respectively of cadmium sulphate solution. For the reverse titrations, theoretical titre values for the formation of the above compounds would be 18.44, 9.22 and 12.30 c.c. respectively of potassium ferrocyanide solution.

The observed titre value in aqueous medium in the case of direct titrations (23.0 c.c.) is slightly higher than the theoretical one required for the formation of $K_2CdFeCy_6$. In the reverse case the observed value (17.0 c.c.) in aqueous medium is lower than the theoretical one required for the formation of the same compound. The discrepancy between the observed and the theoretical titre values can be explained on the tendency of the compound formed to hydrolyse. Then potassium ferrocyanide, thus released,

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

would react with more of cadmium sulphate with the result that the titre values in aqueous solutions would be greater in the direct titrations and less in the reverse titrations.

The effect of addition of alcohol in increasing amounts in direct titrations is to gradually decrease the observed titre values; in the reverse titrations an increase is observed under the same conditions. This can be explained as being due to the check of hydrolysis of the compound. The observed titre values in the presence of increasing amounts of alcohol should thus correspond more closely to the theoretical values in the direct and the reverse titrations. This has been actually observed.

Similar reasoning has been advanced by us in the case of copper ferrocyanide (*cf.* Parts I-III, this *Journal*, 1947, **24**, 487, 499; 1948, **25**, 27).

The adsorption of cadmium and ferrocyanide ions by cadmium ferrocyanide sol has been observed. The adsorption of these ions, from the surrounding solution by the precipitate would be to decrease the titre value in aqueous medium in both the cases, which should then increase in the presence of alcohol. This is observed only in the reverse titrations, whereas there is a decrease in the titre value in the direct titrations in

presence of alcohol. This suggests that the effect of adsorption is masked, and the role of hydrolysis is more predominant during the precipitation of cadmium ferrocyanide. It appears that these facts were not taken into consideration by previous authors and this is the reason that so conflicting views have been expressed on the composition of cadmium ferrocyanide.

A break in the thermometric titration curve corresponding to the formation of $K_2Cd_3(FeCy_6)_2$, obtained in the conductometric study of the compound by Kalthoff (*loc. cit.*), has not been observed. The observation of Treadwell and Chervet (*loc. cit.*) that only in highly dilute solutions the precipitate approximate to the exact composition, $K_2CdFeCy_6$, does not seem to be reproducible, because in highly dilute solutions, the chances of the compound to hydrolyse would be still greater. The observation of Mackay (*loc. cit.*) that it requires about 2.5% less potassium ferrocyanide to precipitate the cadmium salt than would be required by $K_2CdFeCy_6$, supports the viewpoint of hydrolysis of the compound as observed by us.

Thermometric studies therefore support the formation of the compound $K_2CdFeCy_6$, but this is affected by factors like adsorption and hydrolysis.

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